

Our Goals

The aim of the EU-funded Horizon Europe project FAIR2Adapt is to enable the development of comprehensive, scientifically sound climate change adaptation strategies for stakeholders across Europe. Building on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the project makes climate-related data easier to find, share, and reuse. Through six real-world case studies, FAIR2Adapt demonstrates how better data sharing can drive practical climate action across European regions and cities.

The FAIR2Adapt Consortium brings together 18 partners from across 13 European countries, from the Arctic North to the Mediterranean South.

fair2adapt-eosc.eu

FAIR2Adapt

Advancing climate adaptation in Europe

Making climate data easier to find, share, and reuse, so regions and cities across Europe can build stronger, more resilient futures.

About the Project

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable - refers to principles that ensure scientific data can be effectively shared and reused. FAIR2Adapt applies these principles to climate data, making diverse environmental, climatic, and socio-economic datasets easier to find, combine, and use.

The project uses FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) - standardised, machine-actionable packages of research data and metadata - and semantic tools such as the I-ADOPT framework, which aligns scientific terminology across disciplines. These kinds of FAIR tools enable regions to develop scientifically sound adaptation plans and transfer successful solutions to new contexts.

These approaches are put to the test through six real-world case studies across Europe, where FAIR2Adapt demonstrates how better data sharing translates into practical climate action.

Real-World Impact

The project's case studies address diverse climate challenges across Europe:

1. Spreading Radioactive Isotopes in the Arctic under Different Climate Scenarios, Arctic
2. RiOMar Project - Coastal Water Quality Anticipation to Manage Coastal Zone Ecosystem Responses for Biodiversity Conservation, France
3. Hamburg City - Climate-Induced Stressors and their Effects on Urban Societies, Germany
4. Developing and Testing a FAIR-by-Design National Adaptation Hub, Portugal
5. Connecting and Visualising the CCA Knowledge Landscape through the Connectivity Hub and weADAPT, Global
6. FAIRification of a Climate Adaptation Strategy, Pan-European

FAIR2Adapt engages stakeholders through training sessions, webinars, workshops, and hackathons to equip researchers, local authorities, and policymakers with the skills and knowledge to develop effective climate adaptation solutions.

Why it Matters

FAIR2Adapt benefits European stakeholders by supporting evidence-based adaptation planning that builds on existing resources and by helping develop policies that safeguard people and ecosystems.

Together with sister project Climate-Adapt4E-OSC, FAIR2Adapt co-hosts the activity "FAIR & Data Quality" under the Thematic Working Group Climate Services of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, working with practitioners and projects to build shared resources for climate adaptation communities. This shows how collaborative science can turn complex climate data into practical solutions for European communities.

